

"Study Of News Website For Mortgage Industries "

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ABSTRACT

This paper analyzes the news portal for the mortgage industries that gives an appropriate and comfy content show that an outsized population round the world. So will learn and find the information concerning the globe digital info resource serving the whole residential mortgage trade, as well as depositories, nonbank lenders and servicers, brokerage companies, vendors, and regulators. Additionally, to providing news analysis and perspective, NMN convenes trade participants to supply insight on topics as well as regulation, compliance, technology, and loss mitigation. Supply Media could be a business-to-business digital promoting service, subscription info, and event company serving senior-level professionals within the monetary, technology, and health care sectors. Brands embrace Yankee Banker, Payments supply, National Mortgage News, worker profit News.

1. INTRODUCTION

The development of an internet site for web-based newspapers usually suggests that making an internet site within which the management of all items sent by the group concerning any news & activities area unit done by the administrator wherever all folks (viewers). It will be read and apprehend all the user relevant info concerning the information that they obtain. This web site project is concerning the coming up with of an e-news that displays the news that a standard person desires to indicate.

The website portal has mainly three user elements wherever one is registered user (authentication required) World Health Organization will read, add comment will have a general discussion with another user.

The web site consists of basic pages from that the user will read and understand the relevant info like history, upcoming

The main aim of the web site project is meant to develop a portal for the management of Web-based e-news. The web site portal provides a chunk of appropriate data and shows that an oversized population around the world will learn or can have information regarding the planet. This is often a crowdsourcing e-news. The thought is anyone will send point mistreatment their web-based appliance, that is managed by the administrator to whom the editor's panel unbroken to blame of this to form it visible for the plenty. This web site portal is developed mistreatment PHP, HTML & CSS technologies, and SQL Server.

In other cases, the administrator manages all the relevant actions for which the users can view properly and also make reports. The model for this project is similar to the link (<http://business.timesonline.co.in.uk>) as given, and for quick development and ease of use, we selected to implement "Wordpress." In this project, Wordpress is installed over xampp. As we did not

know how to use and setup Wordpress.

Developing e-newspaper portals not a cakewalk activity as it has to be different from other commercial website portals.

These Publish publication

s, articles, columns, press releases, blogs, and other news related content from all across the globe. The mortgage industry of the United States is a major financial sector. The federal government created several programs, or government-sponsored entities, to foster mortgage lending, construction and encourage homeownership.

EVERY NEWS PORTAL MUST HAVE THE FOLLOWING FEATURES:

- Manage different types of users like admin, editor, reporter
- Login for users
- Users dashboard where reporter and editor can see their news posted
- Manage Categories
- Upload news on a specific category
- Highlight featured story
- Publish/ Unpublish news
- Manage video interviews

2 REVIEW OF LITERATURE

1. Portal Information Gathering
2. Set goals for a newspaper website
3. Define the target audience of the website
4. Create a sitemap sketch
5. Create a wireframe /mockup
6. Design
7. Change the layout when the required
8. Content Writing and Assembly
9. page layout
10. Coding
11. Consider SEO friendly design
12. Regular Updating and Maintenance
12. Adding user report system
13. finding and Fix bugs asap
14. Keep website update

3. OBJECTIVES

To study customized e-news website portal development & news

portal website design

- To study the

- integrated content management system & robust maintenance and support website system
- To study easy managing administration panel
- To study Multi-language support
- To study of user interface on different devices

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The following methodology has been used in this study.

Type Of Research:

Analytical Research:

Data analysis done by using Analytical Research Methodology and Primary Data collection method is used. The analysis is the process of comparing and gathering portal information about the website and its operation and use in order to improve the overall website quality of design and to identify problem areas.

The purpose of the web site analysis is to get answers to queries through the appliance of Procedures. The most aim of the portal analysis is to search out out the reality that is hidden not been discovered up to now. Although each and every analysis study has its own specific purpose, we tend to might imagine portal analysis object lives. To test a project

hypothesis of a crucial relationship between variables (such studies are called hypothesis-testing analysis studies)

Web Development Methodology

- Waterfall Methodology

The waterfall model can offer a clear organizational or agency structure for website development projects, in which the individual website project phases are clearly separated from each other. Since each phase concludes with a milestone, the website development process is easy to follow. The model focuses on the documentation of the following process steps.

- Requirements analysis
- Getting to know a client
- Formulate digital strategy
- Wireframes and prototypes creation
- Web Development
- Data Migration phase
- Pre-deployment phase
- Quality assurance
- Post-launch QA and maintenance
- Waterfall Methodology

5. DATA COLLECTION

It includes descriptive facts on numerical information, quantitative and qualitative information. The collection of data is an important stage in research. The quality of data determines the quantity of research.

- 1) PRIMARY DATA: Gathered through in-depth conversations, electronic surveys, Live chat, Email, Telephone interview, or a series of informal discussions.

6. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

After the data has been analyzed and summarized, the next step is linking the portal results with the research objectives, can be stated clearly the implications of the findings, and doing all this with our objective and rational approach.

- Gathering Information
 - 1) Set the website goals
 - 2) Define the target audience of the website
- Planning
 - 1) sitemap creation
 - 2) Create a mockup/ wireframe
 - 3) Select technologies platform (framework,CMS,programming language)
- Design
 - 1) Create a colorful page layout
 - 2) layout
- Review
 - 3) feedback on the layout from the client
 - 4) Change the layout as per client requirement
- 1) Create new original content
 - 2) Get original content ready for migration

- Coding
 - 1) Build and deploy the website
 - 2) Add special features and interactivity
 - 3) SEO friendly website

- Testing Review & launch
 - 1) Test the created website
 - 2) Upload the website on the server
 - 3) Final testing and launch

- Maintenance and Regular Updating
 - 1) Add user report system
 - 2) Fix bugs asap
 - 3) Keep website up to date

1) Which technology is best for web site development?

- a) PHP
- b) ASP.NET
- c) RUBY ON RAILS
- d) DJANGO
- e) J2EE

2) Define your purpose for the web site and, therefore, the targeted audience.

A targeted audience profile is solely a particular cluster of users possibly to retort completely and sensible to your promotions, products, and services. Often, your target folk's analysis is going to be supported by specific factors like age, income, location, and so on.

3) How secure is your newspaper website?

Newspaper web site} security is any action or application taken to make sure site knowledge isn't exposed to cybercriminals or to forestall the exploitation of stories websites in any method.

3) Is it customized & Easy to navigate the design of the news portal website?

Online news portal web site development ought to offer readers the chance to customize their home page, giving them the facility to decide on sections, topics, contents of their interest.

4) How do I get my news website to rank higher on Google?

Ranking on SERP involves optimizing your news website with the Longtail keywords and design to ensure it appears high in relevant SERP. To learn how to top rank higher on Google, start with original content creation and SEO, which can help to drive high organic traffic and increase exposure for your news website.

7. FINDINGS

1. Improve User Experience & Online Conversions
2. Fix Page Errors
3. Address Title and Meta Issues
4. Check for Navigation & Usability Issues
5. Determine Web Design Mobile Responsiveness
6. Uncover Issues Slowing Page Load Speed
7. Ensure Content Converts Visitors to Leads, Sales
8. Make it Easy for Prospects to Contact You
9. Identify Elements That Increase Bounce Rates
10. Be Up-to-speed with Google Algorithm Updates

8. SUGGESTION

- Website Navigation
- Mobile-friendly
- Internal Linking
- Email Sign Up Forms
- Speed optimization
- SEO Friendly
- Advertisement (Third-party ads)
- Lead Management

9. CONCLUSION

After process through all phases of the web site system development life cycle, the portal is developed. Within the future, it'll be hosted on the online server, which is able to be accessed by all individuals within the world and might read the location and learn the maximum amount of news and data concerning the planet. The administrator or editor UN agency is appointed for redaction or managing knowledge or dominant are given the secure credentials info and can amendment or modify the location as per the wants.

Also, in the future, we can add many features to support i-pads, i-phone, and other electronic devices. It helps you to develop in a personalized manner. It helps your business to get engaged with the prospective customer. This project that helps the people and make them aware so that they can know any news.

10. REFERENCE

WEBSITES:

1. <https://stackoverflow.com/>
2. <https://www.w3schools.com/>
3. https://codex.wordpress.org/Function_Reference
4. <https://css-tricks.com/>
5. <https://www.quora.com/>
6. <https://wordpress.org/>
7. <https://theforest.net/>